

CIEAESM4015: HONOURS PROGRAMME MASTER THESIS

Measured change in bed elevation and surface texture near longitudinal training dams in the Waal River

FINAL REPORT

Author:

R.J.A. VAN WEERDENBURG
4292847

Supervisors:

A. BLOM
H.A.P. EERDEN
A. CROSATO

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Abstract

In 2015 three longitudinal training dams (LTDs) were constructed in the Waal River as a pilot project to assess the performance of LTDs in the field. The LTDs in the Waal River separate a side channel in the inner bend from the main channel in the outer bend over a river reach of 12 *km*. In this study changes in bed elevation and surface texture near the pilot LTDs are presented based on field data and possible causes for the observed changes are discussed.

Changes in the bed elevation are studied from April 2011 till March 2018. This is done along one-dimensional profiles and by considering the average bed elevation per river reach. The results show bed lowering in the main channel during the construction of LTDs. The bed elevation in the deepest part of the side channels increased rapidly in the first year after construction. Downstream of the LTDs a trough started to develop during construction and the size of that trough increased in the years after construction. At the upstream end of the reach of the pilot LTDs a sedimentation front developed.

Changes in the surface texture are studied based on the D_{50} , D_{10} and D_{90} of sediment samples that were obtained in fall 2017 relative to samples from 1966, 1976, 1984 and 1995. The results on changes in the surface texture are presented together with an indication of the amount of spreading in the data. The results show no clear change in the average characteristics of the surface texture per cross-section from rkm 908 to rkm 925. In general, the surface texture in the side channels is finer than the surface texture in the main channel.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Context

In 2015 three longitudinal dams were constructed in the Waal River between Wamel and Ophemert. The design, construction, monitoring and evaluation of the longitudinal training dams form a pilot project called WaalSamen, in which various stakeholders aim to find an integral solution for several problems in river management (Rijkswaterstaat, 2016). The three longitudinal training dams (LTDs) replace the transverse groynes in two subsequent inner bends of the river, as shown in the satellite image in Figure 1.1. As can be seen in this figure, the LTDs divide the river into a main channel in the outer bend and a smaller side channel in the inner bend.

Figure 1.1: Satellite image obtained from Google Earth showing the position and the orientation of the three longitudinal training dams in the Waal River between Wamel and Ophemert. The arrows indicate the flow direction and the LTDs are highlighted using white lines. The right image zooms in to the upstream side channel being separated from the main channel by an LTD.

The replacement of groynes by LTDs in the Waal River aims to increase the conveyance capacity during high flow rates, while maintaining sufficient flow depth for navigation during low flow rates. In serving this aim, the construction of LTDs has been an alternative for lowering of the groynes as part of the Room for the River Programme (Rijkswaterstaat, 2012). LTDs yield a two-channel river system. The spatial variability in flow velocities is expected to yield ecologically more favourable conditions. Sills are located in the inlets of side channels and the height of these sills may be adjusted. The division of water and sediment over main channel and side channel may, to some extent, be controlled by adjusting the height of the sills (van Linge, 2017; Jammers, 2017). The optimum height of the sills reduces the amount of dredging works by stabilizing the river bed, which is another objective of the construction of LTDs (Rijkswaterstaat, 2012).

1.2 Bed stabilization

The Rhine River has been trained since the 19th century to prevent ice masses from obstructing the Rhine River, which may lead to flooding. This has mainly been done by the construction of many transverse dams - which are called groynes - that fix the position of the river over time. The training works changed the Waal River from an anabranching system to a single, meandering channel being deep enough to be intensively used for navigation.

Because of the training works the Rhine River branches have become narrower. This caused the sediment transport capacity of the river to increase, whereas the upstream sediment supply did not increase accordingly. As a result, the river adjusts towards a new equilibrium state in which the bed slope is smaller than in the original situation. Because of the length over which the river has been narrowed the change in bed slope over this length causes considerable degradation of the river bed. The river is tilting around its downstream end and bed degradation is thus more severe further upstream (Jansen et al., 1994). Another cause of bed degradation in the Rhine River branches is excessive dredging in the past: large amounts of sand and gravel were mined from the river bed (Mosselman et al., 2004). The dredging procedure was adjusted in 1992, by which extraction of sediment was not allowed anymore for dredging works upstream of Zaltbommel. Currently, dredged sediment is returned to the river bed in deeper parts of the river (Ten Brinke et al., 2001).

Locally, the bed level in the upstream parts of the Dutch rivers Waal, Nederrijn and IJssel lowers up to 30 mm per year, averaged over the period from 1973 till 2000 (Verweij, 2016). Frings et al. (2014) conducted a study on the sediment budget of the Niederrhein (rkms 640 - 866) and found an average bed level lowering in this river section of 3 mm per year in the period 1991-2010. The most downstream part of the Niederrhein (rkm > 842) is subject to more severe erosion up to 15 mm per year, which corresponds to an analysis by Sieben (2012) mentioned in Verweij (2016). Among other effects, bed degradation threatens the stability of hydraulic structures and barely erodible layers impose a reduction on the draught of ships (Blom, 2016). The coarsening of the sediment supply from upstream may have an additional contribution to the bed degradation (Blom, 2016).

Although the LTDs in the Waal River aim to stabilize the river bed, Le et al. (2018) finds that the bifurcation that is formed by an infinitely high longitudinal training dam is inherently unstable. Whether the main channel or the side channel silts up is influenced by the location of the upstream end of the wall with respect to alternate bars.

The construction of LTDs is a pilot project to investigate whether the intervention serves its objectives in practice. A thorough analysis of the field data, which is obtained by the monitoring programme, is required to assess the effects of LTDs. In relation to what was discussed in this section, an analysis of field data on the river bed is needed to assess whether the changes in the river bed elevation and surface texture contribute to reaching the objectives of LTDs.

1.3 Objectives

This study aims to investigate the measured change in bed elevation and surface texture near the LTDs in the Waal River, in order to assess the effects of the pilot LTDs in the field. The study aims to answer the following research questions:

1. How has the bed elevation changed over time in the river reach where pilot LTDs were constructed?
2. How has the bed surface texture changed over time in the river reach where pilot LTDs were constructed?

1.4 Methodology

Answers to the research questions will be based on an analysis of field data.

The first stage of the project aims to answer the first research question. The bed level in the two-channel system has been monitored by multibeam echosounding, which has provided bed elevation data with a resolution of $1\text{ m} \times 1\text{ m}$. The bed elevation data is going to be used in two different ways. First, one-dimensional bed elevation profiles will be extracted from the grid, both in longitudinal and in lateral direction. Since this study focuses on large scale bed level changes, the bed elevation profiles will be filtered from small-scale bedforms using a moving average filter. The window size of the moving average filter will be based on the dominant bedform lengths in the Waal River. Secondly, the average bed elevation of different river reaches will be determined at times before, during and after the construction of LTDs. The analysis aims to provide insight in the stability of the two-channel system in the field.

The second stage of the project relates to the second research question and aims to present temporal changes in the bed surface texture. Sediment samples were taken from the river bed in 1966, 1976, 1984, 1995, 2007 and 2017. Also, the spatial differences in surface texture in the two-channel system are going to be discussed (sampled in 2017).

1.5 Related research

Two PhD-students in a research programme called RiverCare study the effects of the pilot LTDs in the Waal River (RiverCare, 2016). Timo de Ruijsscher (Wageningen UR) studies the processes that determine the division of water and sediment over the main channel and the side channel in order to optimize the design of LTDs. He uses a physical scale model in his research to study the flow divide at the entrance of a side channel (Huisman et al., 2018). Frank Collas (Radboud University Nijmegen) analyses the variation among species in their sensitivity to (multiple) environmental factors near LTDs (e.g. Collas et al., 2018).

The pilot project is initiated and will eventually be evaluated by Rijkswaterstaat and the partners of pilot project WaalSamen. Whether the LTDs serve its objectives in practice is going to be evaluated on five topics, namely (i) technical aspects (hydraulics & morphology), (ii) ecology, (iii) human experience, (iv) management & maintenance and (v) costs.

Chapter 2

System description

This chapter discusses the characteristics of the river reach where LTDs were constructed. It aims to provide insight in the processes that affect the river bed in this reach.

2.1 Planform

Three LTDs were constructed in the Waal River between August 2014 and October 2015. Figure 2.1 shows a schematic top view of the two-channel system. The upstream LTD (near the village of Wamel) is located on the left side of the main channel between rkm 911.8 and rkm 914.6. The second LTD (near the village of Dreumel) is also located on the left side of the main channel, between rkm 915.0 and rkm 918.3. The downstream LTD (near the village of Ophemert) is located on the right side of the main channel between rkm 918.5 and rkm 921.3 (Rijkswaterstaat, 2012).

Figure 2.1: Schematic top view of the two-channel system which also indicates the locations of the Amsterdam Rijnkanaal (A), a pipeline (B), a ferry quay (C) and a side channel through wetlands (D). The width is indicated and the wide arrow indicates the direction of flow. The kilometers along the river are also indicated. The figure is not drawn to scale. Source of information: Rijkswaterstaat (2012).

At rkm 913.4 the Amsterdam Rijnkanaal connects to the Waal River (A in Figure 2.1). At rkm 914 a pipeline crosses the channel below the river bed and because of only a small cover in the side channel a fixed layer was constructed in the side channel. The location of the pipeline is indicated in Figure 2.1 by the letter B. A bit further downstream, at rkm 914.8, a small ferry crosses the river. The ferry sails through the gap between the two upstream LTDs. The ferry's quay at the inner bend of the river separates the most upstream side channel from the second side channel, as is indicated in Figure 2.1 by the letter C. A satellite image of the river near the ferry quay is included in Figure 2.2. In 2016 the wetlands of Passewaaij were connected to the main river channel at rkm 916.2. The area is shown in the satellite image in Figure 2.3 and its location is indicated by the letter D in Figure 2.1. The outflow from the main channel is located in the outer bend of the main channel on the opposite side of the second LTD. The flow of the wetlands back into the main channel is at rkm 917.3. During average flow rates the discharge through the wetlands is approximately 2% of the total discharge through the river system.

Figure 2.2: Satellite image (obtained from Google Earth) that shows the ferry quay near Tiel at rkm 914.8; its location is indicated by the letter C in Figure 2.1. The ferry quay separates the two most upstream side-channels. Locally the width of the river is 260 m.

Figure 2.3: Satellite image (obtained from Google Earth) that shows the open connection between the main river channel and the wetlands of Passewaaij. The arrows indicate the direction of flow. The location of the wetlands is indicated in Figure 2.1 by the letter D.

The river axis of the two-channel system is defined in the middle of the main channel, which is 115 m away from the groynes in the outer bend. In the single channel the river axis was defined 130 m from the groynes in the outer bend. This implies that the river axis has moved to the right along the two upstream LTDs and to the left along the downstream LTD. The maximum shift of the river axis is 15 m.

2.2 Cross section

The width of the Waal River (referred to as the 'normaalbreedte' in Dutch) used to be defined as the distance between two groynes at opposite sides of the river, measured perpendicular to the river axis. Before the construction of the LTDs the width of the river was uniform and equal to 260 m. Groyne fields were located outside the normal width of the river. The construction of LTDs has created a system of two channels, where groynes are only present in the outer bend of the main channel. The normal width of the main channel is now defined as the distance from the crest of the LTD in the inner bend to the groynes in the outer bend, measured perpendicular to a newly defined river axis of the main channel. According to these definitions, the construction of LTDs has reduced the width of the main channel from 260 m to 230 m, as shown schematically in Figure 2.4 (Rijkswaterstaat, 2012).

Figure 2.4: Illustration of how the cross section of the river has changed. (a) shows the original cross section with groyne fields in both the inner and the outer bend and (b) shows the cross section with an LTD in the inner bend and groynes in the outer bend. The width of the main channel is indicated. Source: Rijkswaterstaat (2012)

At the upstream end of the inlet of Wamel's side channel the width of the main channel is 260 m and over the first 1500 m it gradually decreases to 230 m. Downstream of the LTDs, the groynes are extended to ensure a gradual transition from a width of the main channel of 230 m back to a width of 260 m downstream. At bankfull discharge the width of the side channels is on average 90 m. There are no groynes present in the inner bend of the side channels, hence the position of the inner bank of the side channels is not fixed. Bank erosion was observed during a field trip. The amount of erosion of the inner bank has not been quantified yet.

The height of the crest of the three LTDs is based on the water level during a constant discharge at Lobith of $2606 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ (Eerden et al., 2011). This implies that the LTDs are emerged as long as the discharge at Lobith does not exceed $2606 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. The height of the sills at the inlets of the side channels is OLR-1.25 m^1 . The height of the sills in the inlets may be adjusted in the future.

¹OLR is the 'Agreed Lower River Level' ('Overeengekomen Lage Rivierwaterstand' in Dutch), which is the water level in the Waal River that is exceeded 95% of time, provided the river is free from ice (Eerden et al., 2011).

2.3 Construction works

The construction of LTDs started in August 2014 with the construction of the downstream LTD. Subsequently the second and the upstream LTD were constructed and the final construction works were finished in October 2015. The contractor that was responsible for the construction works was allowed to dredge sediment from the river bed to fill the core of the three LTDs. A rough estimation of the volume of sediment that was needed to fill the core of the three LTDs is made by considering the length of the three LTDs and the cross section of the LTDs. This rough calculation shows that $550\,000\text{ m}^3$ of material was needed for construction. This volume was partly dredged from the river bed and partly obtained by the excavation of the side channels.

In addition to the volume of sediment that was used to fill the core of the LTDs, there are indications that even more sediment was dredged from the river bed during the construction period (Eerden, 2018).

2.4 Dredging works

Dredging works take place in the main channel of the Waal River to provide sufficient flow depth for navigation. The minimal navigation dimensions of the Waal River are defined in the *Acte van Mannheim* to be a depth of 2.8 m over a width of 150 m (Eerden et al., 2011). The dredging works are done by contractors, based on a performance-based contract. Occasionally, the river bed is levelled by shifting the sediment from a shallow area towards the closest trough; a process called ploughing. In practice, the sediment of a river dune's crest is moved into the closest through. In exceptional cases bed material is dredged by a dredging vessel that subsequently deposits the material in a deeper part of the river. The side channels were dredged for the first time in April 2018.

For this study, no specific information was available on the dredging activities in the river. It remains unknown what locations were dredged, where the dredged material was deposited, how much bed material was dredged and what the characteristics of the dredged material were.

2.5 Additional characteristics of the Waal River

This section discusses several other characteristics of the Waal River that are of relevance to understand the behaviour of the river system.

Hydrograph

The average discharge in the Waal River in the period from 1989 to 2014 is $1543\text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ (Jammers, 2017). Figure 2.5 shows the measured discharge in the Waal River at the Pannerdensche Kop bifurcation from January 2011 till April 2018. The Pannerdensche Kop bifurcation is located 45 kilometers upstream of the LTDs. The horizontal lines in Figure 2.5 show the average discharge in the Waal River and the discharge during which the water level is approximately equal to the crest of the LTDs ($2606\text{ m}^3/\text{s}$). The figure gives an indication of the amount of times the LTDs will be submerged: in the period from January 2011 till April 2018 the discharge exceeded the threshold of $2606\text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ on average 2.2 times per year.

Figure 2.5: Discharge in the Waal River at Pannerdensch Kop from January 2011 till April 2018. The horizontal lines show the average discharge and the threshold for overtopping of the LTDs.

Navigation

The Waal River is intensively used for navigation, since it is used as a major shipping route between the port of Rotterdam and the industrial areas of western Germany Ten Brinke et al. (2004). The annual volume of cargo transported on the Dutch Rhine branches is 310 million tons (Blom, 2016), of which a large part is transported on the Waal River. Ship induced currents and waves affect the river bed, as discussed by e.g. Ten Brinke et al. (2004)

Bedforms

The bedforms in the Waal River are studied by Van der Mark and Blom (2007). According to this study, the wavelengths of dominant bedforms in a reach in the Waal River are 63 m, 106 m and 205 m. Bedforms of wavelength between 10 m and 100 m are characterised by Gutierrez et al. (2013) to be large river dunes. Bedforms having wavelengths longer than 100 m are characterised to be river bars. According to these classes the characteristic length scale of river dunes in the Waal River is 63 m and river bars of length scales 106 m and 205 m are observed.

Recent interventions in the Waal River

In the last two decades about 30 projects in the Dutch river system have been completed as part of the Room for the River Programme (RVDR). The programme aimed to increase the safety against flooding by increasing the conveyance capacity of the river system and to improve the spatial quality of the river landscape simultaneously (Rijkswaterstaat Ruimte voor de Rivier). Sloff et al. (2014) studies the cumulative effect of all Room for the River interventions on bed levels and dredging works compared to a reference situation with no interventions. In general, the study predicts the RVDR interventions to cause sedimentation in the conveyance channel. Directly up- and downstream of the longitudinal training dams the groynes were lowered as part of the RVDR programme. The morphodynamic response to these interventions will also affect the reach of LTDs.

Chapter 3

Measurement techniques and data processing

This chapter describes the methods by which field data has been obtained and how the data has been processed and analysed in this study.

3.1 Bed elevation

Data

Field data on the bed elevation in the Waal River was obtained by multi-beam echo sounding measurements by order of Rijkswaterstaat. The measured bed elevations are projected on a regular grid of $1 \times 1 \text{ m}^2$ by averaging the available bed elevation measurements (at least 10) within each grid cell. Bed elevation data from April 2011 till March 2018 is used in this study. The bed elevation of the two-channel system was determined since the construction of LTDs was finished in October 2015.

Data analysis

The first part of the analysis on bed level change uses the bed elevation along one-dimensional profiles, both in longitudinal and in lateral direction. The measured data shows river bedforms as oscillations around the average bed elevation. The characteristics of bedforms in the Waal River were discussed in Chapter 2. As this study focuses on larger scale changes the one-dimensional profiles are filtered by a moving average. To filter river dunes with a characteristic wavelength of 63 m from the bed elevation profile the window size of the moving average is determined 10 times larger than the characteristic wavelength of dunes. The bed elevation along one-dimensional profiles is then presented by a moving average of the original data with a window size of 630 m in longitudinal direction. In lateral direction the bed elevation is averaged over a width of 5 m . Figure 3.1 shows, as an example, the measured bed elevation along the river axis of the main channel in April 2014 and the moving average with a window size of 630 m .

The use of a moving average filter implies that the filtered bed elevation at a certain location is determined as the average bed elevation of an area of length 630 m and width 5 m parallel to the river axis. For example: The bed elevation at rkm 915.5 and 20 m left of the river axis is determined as the average bed elevation of an area of 5 m width (17.5 m to 22.5 m left of the axis) parallel to the river axis from rkm 915.185 to rkm 915.815.

The second part of the analysis on bed level change is based on the average bed elevation per reach. The average bed elevation of eight different reaches is considered from 2011 till 2018. For each of the years the bed elevation in spring (April) and in fall (October) is considered. The locations of the eight reaches are listed in Table 3.1 and illustrated schematically in Figure 3.2. Along each of the three LTDs one reach is located in the main channel and one in the side channel. In addition, two reaches are defined up- and downstream of the LTDs. The left and right boundary of each area in the main channel are chosen 15 m away from groyne heads and the crest of the LTDs. The left and right boundary are indicated relative to the newly defined river axis. The width of the side channel varies with the water level. The water level during monitoring events, thus, determines the width over which the bed elevation was determined. The width of the reach in the side channels has been chosen such that the data obtained by all monitoring events covered the full reach. The average bed elevation per reach has been determined twice per year; in spring (April) and in fall (October).

Figure 3.1: Measured bed elevation along the river axis in April 2014 and the moving average with a window size of 630 m of the original data.

Figure 3.2: Sketch of the river planform and the locations of the eight reaches over which the bed elevation is averaged. The exact locations are listed in Table 3.1. The figure is not drawn to scale.

Reach	Upstream end	Downstream end	Left boundary	Right boundary
Upstream (0)	rkm 910.0	rkm 911.0	RA - 115 m	RA + 115 m
Main channel Wamel (1.1)	rkm 911.8	rkm 914.6	RA - 100 m	RA + 100 m
Side channel Wamel (1.2)	rkm 911.8	rkm 914.8	RA - 137 m	RA - 162 m
Main channel Dreumel (2.1)	rkm 915.0	rkm 918.3	RA - 100 m	RA + 100 m
Side channel Dreumel (2.2)	rkm 915.0	rkm 918.3	RA - 137 m	RA - 162 m
Main channel Ophemert (3.1)	rkm 918.5	rkm 921.3	RA - 100 m	RA + 100 m
Side channel Ophemert (3.2)	rkm 918.5	rkm 921.3	RA + 137 m	RA + 162 m
Downstream (4)	rkm 922.0	rkm 923.0	RA - 115 m	RA + 115 m

Table 3.1: Boundaries of the eight reaches over which the bed elevation is averaged. RA stands for river axis of the main channel. Figure 3.2 shows the eight reaches schematically in the river planform.

3.2 Bed surface texture

Data

In the river reach where LTDs were constructed sediment samples were taken from the upper 10 *cm* of the river bed in 1966, 1976, 1984, 1995 and 2017. Only the method of sampling in 2017 is known and it is assumed that the method of sampling has been similar in other years. In 2017 sediment samples were taken from the river bed surface using a hamon grab. The grain size distributions of the bottom samples were determined in the laboratory by sieve analysis.

From 1966, 1976, 1984 and 1995 samples at every kilometer from rkm 908 to rkm 925 are included in the analysis, both along the river axis and 70 *m* left and right of the river axis. The D_{10} , D_{50} and D_{90} of these samples are known (Ten Brinke, 1997). The data from 2017 includes the results of sieve analysis of samples. In addition, the sediment composition of the river bed surface is known for six locations in the side channels.

In Chapter 2 was discussed that the river axis of the two-channel system is defined in the middle of the main channel. In 2017, the sediment samples were taken at locations relative to the newly defined river axis. The bed surface was thus sampled at different locations than before.

Data analysis

The D_{10} , D_{50} and D_{90} of the grain size distribution of samples from the river bed surface is used to assess changes in bed surface texture over time. The D_{50} (D_{10} , D_{90}) is defined as the diameter of the particle that 50 % (10 %, 90 %) of a sample's mass is larger than.

To assess spatial differences in the bed surface texture of the two-channel system, the sediment samples are analysed using the fractions of gravel, sand and silt per sample. The gravel fraction is determined as the mass percentage of grains bigger than 2 *mm*. The sand fraction is determined as the mass percentage of grains smaller than 2 *mm* and bigger than 0.063 *mm*. The silt fraction is the mass percentage of grains smaller than 0.063 *mm*.

Chapter 4

Bed level analysis

4.1 Bed level change along the river axis

This section discusses the change in bed elevation along the river axis of the main channel in the period from April 2011 till March 2018.

The bed elevation along the river axis of the main channel is considered at two moments per year from April 2011 till March 2018. Figure 4.1 shows a moving average of the bed elevation along the river axis from rkm 911 to rkm 923 in the period from April 2011 till April 2014. In this period, the river bed was not yet affected by the construction of LTDs. It follows from this graph that the maximum variability in bed elevation over this period is approximately 40 *cm*. This is shown in Figure 4.1 by the grey area. The grey area shows a width of 40 *cm* (+/ - 20 *cm*) around the mean of the included bed elevation profiles along the river axis. In general, the filtered bed elevation along the river axis was in the period from April 2011 till April 2014 at a level within this reach.

Figure 4.2 shows a moving average of the bed elevation along the river axis of the main channel in 2014 and 2015; in these years the LTDs were constructed. To relate changes in bed elevation during the construction period to the variability in bed elevation in the years before, Figure 4.3 shows the bed elevation in 2014 and 2015 relative to the variability in Figure 4.1. In this figure three sections are indicated in which the bed elevation is clearly outside the grey area.

Figure 4.1: Moving average of the bed elevation along the river axis from April 2011 till April 2014. The window size of the moving average is 630 *m*. The grey area shows a bandwidth of 40 *cm* around the mean bed elevation in this period.

Figure 4.2: Moving average of the bed elevation along the river axis of the main channel from April 2014 till October 2015, during construction of the LTDs. The window size of the moving average is 630 m. The two most upstream LTDs (Wamel and Dreumel) are located on the left of the main channel and the downstream LTD (Ophemert) is located on the right of the main channel.

Figure 4.3: Bed elevation profiles as presented in Figure 4.2 relative to the variability in bed elevation in the period before the construction of LTDs started (2011-2014), indicated by the grey area. Three sections are indicated in which the bed elevation is clearly outside the grey area.

The changes in bed elevation during the construction period may be induced by the dredging works during construction or as an initial response to the LTDs in a two-channel system. It is therefore interesting to study how the observed changes develop since the construction of LTDs was finished. Figure 4.4 shows a moving average of the bed elevation profiles from the moment the construction of LTDs was finished in October 2015 and Figure 4.5 relates the bed elevation in the first years after construction to the variability in bed elevation in the years before the construction of LTDs.

The bed degradation downstream of the LTDs started already in the construction phase (Figure 4.3) and continued in the years after (Figure 4.5). In three years time a trough has developed along the river axis. The maximum depth of the trough is approximately 1 m and the length is approximately 2 km. Likely, the trough developed because the time-averaged sediment transport capacity downstream of the two-channel system is higher than the sediment supplied from the two-channel system. Possible explanations are a shortage of bed material in the two-channel system or a lower transport capacity in the two-channel system than in the single channel. Another possible explanation for the downstream bed degradation is that the trough was caused by construction works and that it is now propagating downstream. Whether the trough is propagating downstream can hardly be assessed based on the few years of field data that is currently available.

In the period from September 2016 till September 2017 the downstream erosion along the river axis did not continue further, whereas the downstream erosion increased relatively much in the period from September 2017 till March 2018. Field data on the bed elevation in the coming years could show whether the downstream erosion continues further. If not, the erosion in the period from September 2017 till March 2018 may be related to the peak flow in January 2018 (observed in the measured hydrograph in Figure 2.5).

Near the opening between the two most upstream LTDs (rkm 914.5) the bed has eroded, especially in the period between September 2017 and March 2018. This location was discussed in Chapter 2, because the most upstream side channel conflues into the main channel and a bit further downstream the second side channel bifurcates from it. At this location it is also of interest whether the erosion in the period from September 2017 till March 2018 is related to the peak flow in January 2018 or whether it is an ongoing process.

On the upstream end of the domain, around rkm 912, significant sedimentation started in the period from April 2015 to October 2015 and continued afterwards till March 2016. The maximum height of the sedimentation front is approximately 75 cm. The sedimentation at the upstream end in the first year after construction is likely an initial response to the flow conditions in the two-channel system: the bed level increased and as a result the flow velocity changed, such that as much sediment could be transported downstream as was supplied from upstream. The bed elevation in the period from September 2016 till March 2018 does not show indications of ongoing sedimentation on the upstream end of two-channel system.

Field data of the coming years could show whether the sedimentation front will propagate downstream or not and whether the sedimentation front becomes wider. In Figure 4.5 it seems like the bed elevation between rkm 913 and rkm 914 increased since October 2015, although the bed elevation in March 2018 does not follow the trend. The bed level increase might be an indication that the sedimentation front is either propagating downstream or that it is widening. A study on the bed elevation over a longer period of time after construction could show whether this is really the case.

4.1. Bed level change along the river axis

Figure 4.4: Moving average of the bed elevation along the river axis of the main channel from October 2015 till March 2018, after the construction of the LTDs. The window size of the moving average is 630 m. The two most upstream LTDs (Wamel and Dreumel) are located on the left of the main channel and the downstream LTD (Ophemert) is located on the right of the main channel.

Figure 4.5: Bed elevation profiles as presented in Figure 4.4 relative to the variability in bed elevation in the period before the construction of LTDs started (2011-2014), indicated by the grey area.

4.2 Bed level change in cross sections

This section discusses the bed elevation in different cross sections along the river, in order to obtain insight in different bed level changes in lateral direction. It thereby shows whether the change in bed elevation along the river axis is representative for a larger part of the cross section. The locations of the cross sections that are used in this study are indicated in the river planform in Figure 4.6.

Figures showing the bed elevation in the cross sections at different moments in time are included in A. The observations made regarding the change in bed elevation in the cross sections are as follows:

- The fluctuating bed elevation in cross section 1 corresponds to what was observed in Figure 4.5 on the bed elevation along the river axis. The bed elevation fluctuates more on the left side of the channel, which is the side of the inlet to the upstream side channel (Figure A.1).
- In cross section 2, the bed elevation in the side channel is increasing over time. The bed elevation in the left part of the main channel has been increasing from October 2015 till September 2016, but it has been degrading again till January 2018 (Figure A.2). The sedimentation front discussed in Section 4.1 appears thus most severe on the left side of the main channel.
- In cross section 4, the bed elevation in the side channel has not significantly increased, as is the case in all other cross sections that are considered in this section (Figure A.4).
- In cross section 5, the bed level has increased more on the left side of the main channel than on the right side (Figure A.5).
- In cross section 6, the side channel is located on the right side of the main channel. The bed level in the side channel has increased significantly and so did the bed level in the left part of the main channel (Figure A.6).

Figure 4.6: Sketch of the river planform in which the locations of ten cross sections are indicated. The figure is not drawn to scale.

- Downstream of the LTDs the erosion is most severe on the right side of the main channel (Figure A.8). The downstream erosion along the river axis was already discussed in Section 4.1. Apparently, the downstream erosion is strongest on the side of the outlet from the downstream side channel.
- Cross section 9 (Figure A.9) shows that the erosion between September 2017 and March 2018, as discussed in Section 4.1, is concentrated on the left side of the main channel.
- In cross section 10, the second side channel confluent into the main channel on the left and the most downstream side channel bifurcates from the main channel on the right. At this location the bed elevation has been increasing in the right part of the main channel (Figure A.10).

Explanations for the observations may relate to the locations of the side channels.

Downstream of the downstream LTD the bed has eroded most severely on the side of the side channel's outflow. The discharge from the side channel may cause an increase in the sediment transport capacity downstream of the confluence, leading to bed degradation if the sediment supply from the downstream side channel is limited.

Downstream of the second LTD the bed accreted most severely on the side of the side channel's outflow. Apparently the sediment supply to this location exceeds the sediment transport capacity. The sediment may be supplied from the second side channel. That explanation would raise the question why relatively much sediment is transported through the second side channel, whereas the sediment supply from the downstream side channel is not sufficiently high to prevent erosion. To answer that question more insight in the physical processes that determine the division of water and sediment at exchange gaps in a two-channel system is required.

4.3 Average bed level change per reach

A next analysis of bed level change is based on the average bed level in eight different reaches from 2011 till 2018. The locations of the eight reaches were discussed in Section 3.1. The average bed elevation in the main channel and the side channel along the first LTD (Wamel), indicated as reaches 1.1 and 1.2 in Figure 3.2, are shown in Figure 4.7. Figure 4.8 and Figure 4.9 show the average bed elevation in both channels along the second LTD (Dreumel, reaches 2.1 and 2.2) and the third LTD (Ophemert, reaches 3.1 and 3.3).

In all three reaches in the main channel the lowest river bed was observed during the construction phase. A likely explanation for the bed level lowering during construction is the use of bed material for the construction of the LTDs and additional mining of bed material during the construction phase. This has been discussed in Chapter 2. After the construction of LTDs was finished the average bed elevation increased in all three reaches in the main channel. A few years after the construction of LTDs the average bed elevation is roughly at a similar level as before the construction of LTDs.

Chapter 3 discussed that the average bed elevation of the reaches in the side-channels was determined over a width that was covered by the data of all monitoring events. The average bed elevation of reaches in the side channels should therefore be interpreted as the average bed elevation in the deepest part of the side channels. The average bed elevation in the deepest part of the three side channels has increased much since the construction of LTDs. The bed level increase ($\approx 50 - 80 \text{ cm}$) took mainly place in the first year after construction. In the upstream side channel the average bed elevation increased further since fall 2016.

Figure 4.7: Average bed level in the main channel (left axis) and in the deepest part of the side channel (right axis) along the upstream LTD (Wamel, areas 1.1 and 1.2 in Figure 3.2). The start and the end of the construction of LTDs are indicated by the dashed lines. The scales of the two vertical axes differ.

Figure 4.8: Average bed level in the main channel (left axis) and in the deepest part of the side channel (right axis) along the second LTD (Dreumel, areas 2.1 and 2.2 in Figure 3.2). The start and the end of the construction of LTDs are indicated by the dashed lines. The scales of the two vertical axes differ.

Figure 4.9: Average bed level in the main channel (left axis) and in the deepest part of the side channel (right axis) along the downstream LTD (Ophemert, areas 3.1 and 3.2 in Figure 3.2)). The start and the end of the construction of LTDs are indicated by the dashed lines. The scales of the two vertical axes differ.

The difference in bed elevation between the main channel and the side channel is similar for the two most upstream side channels: the bed elevation in the deepest part of the side channel is approximately 145 *cm* higher than the bed elevation in the main channel. The difference between the two channels along the downstream LTD is much smaller: approximately 40 *cm*.

Figure 4.10 and Figure 4.11 show the bed elevation from 2011 to 2018 averaged over the upstream area (area 0 in Figure 3.2) and over the downstream area (area 4 in Figure 3.2). Upstream of the LTDs the average bed level lowered approximately 25 *cm* during construction. Four successive data points show no significant changes in the first year after construction. Two data points in 2017 show that the average bed elevation was at roughly the same level as before the construction of LTDs started. The average bed elevation in spring 2018 is lower again.

Downstream of the LTDs the bed level lowered since the construction of LTDs started. Although the average bed elevation increased between some of the successive monitoring events, the trend that is observed from fall 2014 to spring 2018 shows bed degradation. The erosion downstream likely implies that the time-averaged sediment supply to the downstream reach is lower than the time-averaged sediment transport capacity in that reach. This was already discussed in Section 4.1. In this section the bed level lowering during construction was discussed, and relative to October 2015 the average bed elevation increased in both channels. Because the increase in bed elevation required a large volume of sediment in the two-channel system, this may partly explain why the amount of sediment to the downstream reach was lower than the sediment transport capacity downstream of the LTDs.

Figure 4.10: Average bed level in the area upstream of the LTDs (area 0 in Figure 3.2). The start and the end of the construction of LTDs are indicated by the dashed lines.

Figure 4.11: Average bed level in the area downstream of the LTDs (area 4 in Figure 3.2). The start and the end of the construction of LTDs are indicated by the dashed lines.

Chapter 5

Surface texture

This chapter provides an overview of measured data on the sediment characteristics of the river bed surface in the river reach where longitudinal training dams were constructed (rkm 908 - rkm 925). The end of this chapter discusses the differences in surface texture between the main channel and the side channel in the two-channel system.

5.1 Surface texture in the main channel

This section presents the change in bed surface texture in the main channel at five moments in time. The change in surface texture in the Waal River from 1966 till 1995 is discussed by Ten Brinke (1997). The current analysis focuses mainly on the surface texture in 2017 relative to the historical data.

At first, Figure 5.1 shows the D_{50} of sediment samples along the river from rkm 908 to rkm 925, averaged over the cross section. Per cross section three samples are included. The figure gives already an indication of the spatial variability in surface texture. In general, the average D_{50} seems higher than in 1976 and 1984, but based on this figure there is no clear change in D_{50} relative to 1995. Figure 5.3 and Figure 5.5 show respectively the average D_{10} and the average D_{90} per river kilometer. At almost all cross sections the average D_{90} of the sediment samples is lower in 2017 than in 1995 and the D_{10} is lower in most cross sections. It can be seen in Figure 5.5 that in general the D_{90} in 1995 is larger than in 1976 and in 1984.

Figure 5.2, Figure 5.4 and Figure 5.6 show the mean D_{50} , D_{10} and D_{90} in the river reach from rkm 908 to rkm 925 at five moments in time. The average value is based on 54 samples from the bed surface. The data points are included to show the spreading around the mean. It follows from these figures that the mean D_{50} and D_{10} in 1966 are largely influenced by only a few high values. Figure 5.2 confirms the observation from Figure 5.1 that there is in 2017 no clear change in D_{50} relative to 1995.

Figure 5.7, Figure 5.9 and Figure 5.11 show the D_{50} per kilometer along the river respectively on the left side of the main channel, along the river axis and on the right side of the main channel. It follows from these figures that the D_{50} along the river axis is in 2017 at most locations larger than in 1995. In addition, the variation in D_{50} along the river axis is in 2017 relatively large. On the right side of the river the D_{50} is at most locations smaller than in 2017. No clear changes in D_{50} can be observed on the left side of the river according to the data that is presented in Figure 5.7.

To control the observations that were discussed in the previous paragraph, Figure 5.8, Figure 5.10 and Figure 5.12 show the mean D_{50} and the spreading around the mean on respectively the left side of the main channel, along the river axis and on the right side of the main channel. The average value is based on 18 samples from the bed surface. Figures that show the temporal change and spatial variation in D_{10} and D_{90} on the left side of the main channel, along the river axis and on the right side of the main channel are included in Appendix B.

Figure 5.1: D_{50} of the surface texture at every kilometer along the river, averaged over three samples from each cross section.

Figure 5.2: The blue cross indicates the mean D_{50} of samples from the river bed surface from rkm 908 to rkm 925. The black dots are the data points that were presented in Figure 5.1.

Figure 5.3: D_{10} of the surface texture at every kilometer along the river, averaged over three samples from each cross section.

Figure 5.4: The blue cross indicates the mean D_{10} of samples from the river bed surface from rkm 908 to rkm 925. The black dots are the data points that were presented in Figure 5.3.

Figure 5.5: D_{90} of the surface texture at every kilometer along the river, averaged over three samples from each cross section.

Figure 5.6: The blue cross indicates the mean D_{90} of samples from the river bed surface from rkm 908 to rkm 925. The black dots are the data points that were presented in Figure 5.5.

Figure 5.7: D_{50} of the surface texture at every kilometer along the left side of the main channel.

Figure 5.8: The blue cross indicates the mean D_{50} of the river bed surface on the left side of the main channel from rkm 908 to rkm 925. The black dots are the data points that were presented in Figure 5.7.

Figure 5.9: D_{50} of the surface texture at every kilometer along the river axis of the main channel.

Figure 5.10: The blue cross indicates the mean D_{50} of the river bed surface along the river axis from rkm 908 to rkm 925. The black dots are the data points that were presented in Figure 5.9.

Figure 5.11: D_{50} of the surface texture at every kilometer along the right side of the main channel.

Figure 5.12: The blue cross indicates the mean D_{50} of the river bed surface on the right side of the main channel from rkm 908 to rkm 925. The black dots are the data points that were presented in Figure 5.11.

The most important observations from the data that is presented in this section is that the bed surface along the river axis is coarser in 2017 than in 1995, whereas the bed surface on the right side of the river is finer than in 1995. As a result, there are no indications that in 2017 the surface texture on the right side of the river was coarser than the surface texture along the river axis, whereas this has been the case at the moments of sampling in 1966, 1976, 1984 and 1995 (Ten Brinke, 1997). In addition, the data shows remarkably much variation in the the D_{50} along the river axis in 2017. No information is available on the change in surface texture in other reaches of the Waal River. Therefore, it is uncertain whether the change in surface texture in this reach is related to the construction of LTDs, which started approximately three years before the bed surface was sampled in 2017.

A possible cause for changes in the surface texture that relates to the construction of LTDs is a changing amount of sediment that is exchanged between the groyne fields and the navigation channel in response to currents and waves induced by navigation, a process discussed by Ten Brinke et al. (2004). Another possible cause of changes in the bed surface in the main channel is that mostly fine bed material is extracted towards the side channels.

The surface texture in 2017 does not show that the surface texture on the right side of the main channel is coarser than along the river axis. Ten Brinke et al. (2004) shows that navigation on the Waal River causes the bed surface to become coarser towards the right side of the river. A possible explanation for the observations in this section may thus be related to the use of the river for navigation. Other important processes that affect lateral sorting are the effects of secondary flow and gravity due to the lateral bed slope (Ikeda et al., 1987). These processes may influence the average grain size characteristics in this river reach because the length of the reach is limited (17 km) and there is a relatively sharp leftward bend in this river reach. Studies that investigate the development of secondary flow and the lateral bed slope in the Waal River and in the two-channel system may provide insight in the causes of less lateral sorting in 2017.

A possible explanation for the spatial variability in D_{50} along the river axis may be the location of sampling relative to the locations of river dunes in combination with coarsening of the sediment supply from upstream. Coarsening of the sediment supply from Germany into the Dutch Rhine branches is discussed by (Blom, 2016). In general, the surface texture in troughs is coarser than at crests of river dunes (Blom et al., 2003). If the sediment supplied from upstream becomes coarser, the troughs of river dunes are expected to become coarser first.

The relatively large spatial variability in D_{50} along the river axis in 2017 may also be caused by the changes in bed elevation that were discussed in Chapter 4. In cases of net degradation or aggradation the surface texture changes because of vertical sorting and grain size selective transport (Blom et al., 2003). At some locations the bed elevation in the main channel changed up to 1 m and the spatial variability in sedimentation and erosion likely induces spatial variabilities in surface texture.

5.2 Surface texture in the two-channel system

In this section the focus is on the spatial differences in the surface texture in the system of two channels, according to data obtained by sediment sampling in fall 2017.

Figure 5.13 shows per location of sampling what the gravel fraction in the upper 10 *cm* of the river bed is. The six samples that were taken from the side channels are indicated by the arrows. The amount of gravel in the samples varies from 1 % to 81 %. In five of the six samples from the side channels the amount of gravel appears relatively low, whereas this is not the case at the upstream end of the third side channel (Ophemert (upstream)). Figure 5.14 indicates the silt fraction ($D < 0.063$ *mm*) per sediment sample. The silt fraction is highest in the three most upstream samples from the side channels (Wamel (upstream), Wamel (downstream) and Dreumel (upstream)).

Table 5.1 lists the characteristics of the sediment samples in four different categories. On average, the bed surface in the side channels is much finer than the bed surface in the main channel, as we saw qualitatively in Figure 5.13 and Figure 5.14. Most likely, calmer flow conditions in the side channels prevent fine particles from erosion from the river bed. In addition, in Chapter 4 was found that the average bed elevation in the side channels had increased much in the first year after the construction of LTDs. Most of the sediment in samples from the side channels will therefore be sediment that is deposited in the side channels after the construction of LTDs.

There is one location in the side channel (Ophemert (upstream)) where the bed surface consists for 66 % out of gravel. Possibly, the flow conditions near the inlet in the downstream side channel are less calm than near the inlets in other side channels. That would imply that fine sediments are eroded from the river bed more easily and the river bed would be coarser than at the upstream ends of the other side channels, as was observed in the data that is presented in this section.

	average gravel fraction	average silt fraction
entire river reach	32.4	0.25
main channel	33.8	0.16
side channel	18.2	1.22

Table 5.1: Characteristics of the surface texture in fall 2017, as graphically presented in Figure 5.13 and Figure 5.14. The average gravel fraction and the average silt fraction are listed for three categories of samples: (i) the two-channel system from rkm 905 to rkm 925, (ii) the main channel and (iii) the side channels.

Figure 5.13: Amount of gravel (as a mass-percentage) in the upper 10 cm of the river bed for all 68 samples that were taken in 2017. The arrows indicate the samples that were taken from the side channels.

Figure 5.14: Amount of silt (as a mass-percentage) in the upper 10 cm of the river bed for all 68 samples that were taken in 2017. The arrows indicate the samples that were taken from the side channels.

Chapter 6

Discussion

In this chapter the limitations and the uncertainties of the results that were presented in the previous chapters are discussed.

6.1 Causes of bed level change

The bed elevation was determined by multibeam echosounding measurements at several moments. The resulting bathymetric data yields snapshots at certain times and nothing is known about the development of the bed level towards the bed level during a monitoring event.

In this study measured changes in bed elevation and surface texture are presented and possible explanations for the changes are discussed. The aim of the study is to obtain insight in the morphodynamic response of the river system to the construction of longitudinal training dams. However, the morphology of the Waal River at a certain moment in time is the result of an interplay of many different processes, in addition to the variability that is induced by the hydrograph. It is therefore hard to appoint changes in the morphology to a certain intervention or to another type of cause, also because the morphological time-scale of the Waal River is relatively large (determined analytically by Jansen et al. (1994)).

Most relevant interventions are 30 projects in the Dutch river system that were completed in the last two decades as part of the Room for the River Programme (Rijkswaterstaat Ruimte voor de Rivier). Other Room for the River projects than the construction of longitudinal training dams have affected the river morphology near the LTDs during the time-span that has been considered in this study.

There are more processes that affect the river morphology, but their effects are not quantified in this study. Dredging works take place in the river reach to guarantee sufficient flow depth for navigation. Dredging works in the main channel disturb the morphodynamic response of the river system to interventions and if dredged material is moved to another river reach the sediment budget of the reaches is affected. The effect of dredging works on the river morphology have not been quantified in this study. This limits the insight in the morphodynamic response to the river intervention that is obtained by the analysis of field data. In addition, the Waal River is intensively used for navigation and the currents and waves that are generated by inland barges affect the river morphology. Furthermore, deposits of sediment in floodplains and groyne fields form a sink of sediments, whereas the erosion of banks, groyne fields and floodplains acts as a source of sediment for the river system.

6.2 Analysis of bed level data

The methods by which changes in bed elevation are analysed and presented in this study influence the results of the study. First of all, one-dimensional bed elevation profiles in longitudinal and lateral direction were extracted from the two-dimensional bathymetry. The location of the one-dimensional profiles determines what part of the original data is presented in this study and what the results of this study eventually are. The locations where one-dimensional profiles were extracted from the two-dimensional bathymetry were selected based on the relevance of changes in bed elevation along these profiles to obtain insight in the morphodynamic response in the river reach.

Moreover, a moving average of the measured data is presented to filter small scale bedforms from the measured data and to focus on large scale changes. This operation modifies the data and the information that is presented in this study. Increasing the window size of the moving average would reduce the magnitude of extremes in the bed elevation, which in turn changes the results of this study. The window size of the moving average in this study is chosen in relation to the characteristic length scale of river dunes in the Waal River. In this way information on bed level changes on the scale of river dunes is filtered from the data, whereas information on bed level changes on larger scales is maintained.

In Chapter 4 the average bed elevation is presented in eight different reaches that are defined in Chapter 3. The boundaries of these reaches affect the results that are presented in Chapter 4. For instance, the reaches in the side channel have a width of only 25 m, because the bed elevation of the most shallow part of the side channel could only be determined by multibeam echosounding measurements during one single monitoring event. The reaches in the side channels do - therefore - only provide information on the average bed elevation in the deepest part of the side channels. Similarly, the reaches in the main channel do not extend over the full width of the main channel.

6.3 Data on the surface texture

For this study data on the surface texture over a reach of 17 km was available. Because of the spatial variation in surface texture the number of samples was too limited to obtain reliable statistics on the surface texture in this reach. The statistics that were determined in Chapter 5 were therefore presented together with an indication of the amount of spreading in the data.

Temporal changes in the surface texture were assessed based on the D_{50} , D_{10} and D_{90} of sediment samples from the river bed surface. However, the characteristics of the bed surface are better characterised by the entire gradation curve. The gradation curves of sediment samples from 1966, 1976, 1984 and 1995 were not available for this study. Therefore, changes in surface texture were analysed based on the three characteristic grain sizes only.

Chapter 7

Conclusions and recommendations

In this study field data has been analysed to obtain insight in measured changes in bed elevation and surface texture near recently constructed longitudinal training dams in the Waal River. The two research questions of this study are:

1. How has the bed elevation changed over time in the river reach where pilot LTDs were constructed?
2. How has the bed surface texture changed over time in the river reach where pilot LTDs were constructed?

Section 7.1 provides answers to the first research question and lists recommendations for future research, which may improve or elaborate on the current study. Section 7.2 relates to the second research question.

7.1 Bed elevation

This section lists answers to the first research question and recommendations that are related to changes in bed elevation.

- In the four years before the construction of LTDs, the maximum variation in bed elevation at a certain location in the river reach from rkm 911 to rkm 923 is in the order of 40 *cm*.
- During the construction period the average bed elevation in the main channel along the three LTDs decreased. The average decrease is in the order of 10 *cm*. The lowering of the river bed during the construction period is probably caused by dredging works, since sediment from the river bed was used to fill the core of the LTDs.
- The average bed elevation in the deepest part of the side channels increased rapidly in the first year after construction. The bed level increase is in the order of 0.5 *m* – 1.0 *m*.
- During the construction period a trough started to develop just downstream of the LTDs. After the construction period the trough developed further, up to a depth of approximately 1 *m* and a length of around 2 *km* along the river axis in March 2018. Based on the results of this study it is uncertain whether the trough propagates downstream.
- On the upstream end of the upstream LTD a sedimentation front in the main channel developed in the first year after construction. The sedimentation front did not increase in height after the first year. The results of this study show indications that the sedimentation front widens and/or propagates in downstream direction. Field data on the bed elevation in the coming years should show whether this is really the case.

Recommendations

- To obtain more insight in the causes of changes in bed elevation, the results of this study can be related to hydrodynamic measurements. The hydrodynamic measurements that are part of the monitoring programme of the pilot project are expected to provide insight in local flow velocities and the division of water over the two-channel system.

- The changes in bed elevation that are presented in this study are measured up to three years after the construction of LTDs was finished. Large changes are observed. Whether the aggradation or degradation at different locations is a continuing process may be assessed when field data over a longer period becomes available.
- Field data on the bed elevation in the coming years will show whether the erosion downstream of the LTDs continues. Currently, the monitoring programme of the pilot project does not monitor the bed elevation downstream of rkm 923. In order to monitor and to evaluate the downstream erosion properly, the reach of the monitoring programme and the evaluation study should be extended in downstream direction.
- An important step in the morphodynamic evaluation of the pilot LTDs would be to set up a sediment balance of the river reach. The contribution of sources and sinks of sediment to changes in the bed elevation in the reach of LTDs will help to relate bed level changes to their cause.

7.2 Surface texture

This section discusses conclusions from this study that are related to the surface texture in the reach of LTDs and it lists recommendations for future studies.

- Data from 1995 and 2017 on the average D_{50} per cross section from rkm 908 to rkm 925 does not show a clear difference. The data shows, in general, a lower D_{10} and D_{90} in 2017 than in 1995.
- In 2017 there are no indications that the surface texture on the right side of the main channel is coarser than along the river axis, whereas this has been the case in 1966, 1976, 1984 and 1995.
- On average, the surface texture in the side channel is finer than the surface texture in the main channel. This conclusion is based on sediment samples that were taken from the river bed in fall 2017. The amount of gravel in samples from the side channels was lower than in samples from the main channel, whereas the amount of silt was higher.

Recommendations

- It is uncertain what the causes of changes in the surface texture are and whether the causes are related to the construction of LTDs. It would therefore be interesting to relate changes in this reach to changes in other reaches of the Waal River.
- The sediment composition of the river bed surface in the two-channel system is going to be determined more often as part of the monitoring programme in the coming years. This yields two interesting options for future research:
 - Temporal changes in the sediment characteristics of the river bed surface in the two-channel system may provide more insight in the morphodynamic development of the two-channel system.
 - An additional dataset that provides information on the surface texture at a moment shortly after fall 2017 will help to get insight in the amount of variation in the data on the sediment characteristics. This helps to address the uncertainty of the results in this study.

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Appendix A

Figures: Bed elevation in cross sections

This appendix shows the bed elevation in ten different cross sections in October 2015, March 2016, September 2016, May 2017, September 2017 and January 2018. The locations of the ten cross sections in the river reach are shown in Figure 3.2. The most important observations that follow from the figures in this appendix are discussed in Section 4.2.

Figure A.1: Bed elevation in cross section 1 (see Figure 4.6) from October 2015 till January 2018. The bed elevation at a certain point has been determined as the average bed elevation of a surrounding area with a length of 630 m and a width of 5 m.

Figure A.2: Bed elevation in cross section 2 (see Figure 4.6) from October 2015 till January 2018. The bed elevation at a certain point has been determined as the average bed elevation of a surrounding area with a length of 630 m and a width of 5 m.

Figure A.3: Bed elevation in cross section 3 (see Figure 4.6) from October 2015 till January 2018. The bed elevation at a certain point has been determined as the average bed elevation of a surrounding area with a length of 630 m and a width of 5 m.

Figure A.4: Bed elevation in cross section 4 (see Figure 4.6) from October 2015 till January 2018. The bed elevation at a certain point has been determined as the average bed elevation of a surrounding area with a length of 630 m and a width of 5 m.

Figure A.5: Bed elevation in cross section 5 (see Figure 4.6) from October 2015 till January 2018. The bed elevation at a certain point has been determined as the average bed elevation of a surrounding area with a length of 630 m and a width of 5 m.

Figure A.6: Bed elevation in cross section 6 (see Figure 4.6) from October 2015 till January 2018. The bed elevation at a certain point has been determined as the average bed elevation of a surrounding area with a length of 630 m and a width of 5 m.

Figure A.7: Bed elevation in cross section 7 (see Figure 4.6) from October 2015 till January 2018. The bed elevation at a certain point has been determined as the average bed elevation of a surrounding area with a length of 630 m and a width of 5 m.

Figure A.8: Bed elevation in cross section 8 (see Figure 4.6) from October 2015 till January 2018. The bed elevation at a certain point has been determined as the average bed elevation of a surrounding area with a length of 630 m and a width of 5 m.

Figure A.9: Bed elevation in cross section 9 (see Figure 4.6) from October 2015 till January 2018. The bed elevation at a certain point has been determined as the average bed elevation of a surrounding area with a length of 630 m and a width of 5 m.

Figure A.10: Bed elevation in cross section 10 (see Figure 4.6) from October 2015 till January 2018. The bed elevation at a certain point has been determined as the average bed elevation of a surrounding area with a length of 630 m and a width of 5 m.

Appendix B

Figures: Surface texture

In this appendix figures are included that show the D_{10} and the D_{90} of the surface texture at five moments in time. Observations that follow from these figures are included in Chapter 5.

Figure B.1: D_{10} of the surface texture at every kilometer along the left side of the main channel.

Figure B.2: The blue cross indicates the mean D_{10} of the river bed surface on the left side of the main channel from rkm 908 to rkm 925. The black dots are the data points that were presented in Figure B.1.

Figure B.3: D_{10} of the surface texture at every kilometer along the river axis of the main channel.

Figure B.4: The blue cross indicates the mean D_{10} of the river bed surface along the river axis from rkm 908 to rkm 925. The black dots are the data points that were presented in Figure B.3.

Figure B.5: D_{10} of the surface texture at every kilometer along the right side of the main channel.

Figure B.6: The blue cross indicates the mean D_{10} of the river bed surface on the right side of the main channel from rkm 908 to rkm 925. The black dots are the data points that were presented in Figure B.5.

Figure B.7: D_{90} of the surface texture at every kilometer along the left side of the main channel.

Figure B.8: The blue cross indicates the mean D_{90} of the river bed surface on the left side of the main channel from rkm 908 to rkm 925. The black dots are the data points that were presented in Figure B.7.

Figure B.9: D_{90} of the surface texture at every kilometer along the river axis of the main channel.

Figure B.10: The blue cross indicates the mean D_{90} of the river bed surface along the river axis from rkm 908 to rkm 925. The black dots are the data points that were presented in Figure B.9.

Figure B.11: D_{90} of the surface texture at every kilometer along the right side of the main channel.

Figure B.12: The blue cross indicates the mean D_{90} of the river bed surface on the right side of the main channel from rkm 908 to rkm 925. The black dots are the data points that were presented in Figure B.11.